

TECHNIQUES FOR TEACHING CHILDREN OF VARIOUS AGES HOW TO
PRONOUNCE CORRECTLY AND CRUCIAL GUIDELINES

Yo'lchiyeva Madina Mexritdin qizi

The student of Chirchik state pedagogical university.

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Abstract. The purpose of this scientific article is to analyze the methods of correct pronunciation of words in learning a foreign language at different ages and levels. This topic has been discussed many times by many linguists, and on the basis of all important approaches, word learners of different ages are now being taught to pronounce correctly. This article reveals many important aspects of pronunciation competence as examples and helps to improve pronunciation competence. As the object of the article, the means and methods of forming the ability to pronounce correctly in different age groups were taken. The analysis of instructions for the use of the same tools and methods is the subject of the work. Monographs and scientific articles completed in our linguistics were used as a theoretical source for scientific work.

Key words: pronunciation, assimilation, segmental aspect, suprasegmental aspect, phonetic categories, speech sounds, stress pattern, learning capacities.

МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ДЕТЕЙ РАЗНОГО ВОЗРАСТА ПРАВИЛЬНОМУ
ПРОИЗНОШЕНИЮ И ВАЖНЫЕ УКАЗАНИЯ

Аннотация. Целью данной научной статьи является анализ методов правильного произношения слов при изучении иностранного языка в разном возрасте и на разных уровнях. Эта тема неоднократно обсуждалась многими лингвистами, и на основе всех важных подходов сейчас учат правильно произносить изучающих слова разного возраста. Эта статья раскрывает многие важные аспекты произношения на примерах и помогает улучшить произношение. В качестве объекта статьи были взяты средства и методы формирования умения правильно произносить слова в разных возрастных группах. Предметом работы является анализ инструкций по использованию тех же средств и методов. Монографии и научные статьи, выполненные по нашему языкознанию, использовались как теоретический источник для научной работы.

Ключевые слова: произношение, ассимиляция, сегментарный аспект, супraseгментарный аспект, фонетические категории, звуки речи, характер ударения, способности к обучению.

INTRODUCTION

Foreign learners find English pronunciation challenging as spelling and pronunciation are unrelated. Furthermore, it is improbable that the speech sounds of English will match exactly with those of the learners' first language. Variations in word stress placement, syllable quality and intensity, speech rhythm, and intonation can occur. Many people often adapt English sounds to match those of their native language and incorporate other aspects of their native language's pronunciation into English. Nevertheless, it is important to avoid assimilation when teaching English pronunciation, and learners must be instructed on the correct segmental and suprasegmental aspects of pronunciation.

Gilakjani suggests that individuals who begin learning English post-school years encounter more challenges in obtaining clear pronunciation, with the level of difficulty rising as they get older. Kralova argues that individuals of any age can develop new phonetic categories for unfamiliar language sounds that differ from those in their native language. The truth is that individuals of all ages are learning English, indicating that focusing on teaching pronunciation is important for both children and adults. Teaching pronunciation in schools is not as highly valued as teaching grammar or vocabulary. This issue is commonly seen in English education across several nations. Experienced educators are hesitant to instruct pronunciation, arguing that textbooks lack clear guidance and that stand-alone exercises are ineffective.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Teachers frequently argue that they do not have sufficient time to dedicate to teaching pronunciation in their classes, as they feel more comfortable teaching grammar and vocabulary.

Teachers also express dissatisfaction with the lack of sufficient training in teaching pronunciation methodology. Despite the challenging nature of English pronunciation, there is limited focus on teaching and improving it. According to Haycraft, foreign English teachers do not focus on teaching pronunciation because they lack confidence in their own abilities.

You may have successfully surrounded your child with books to instill a reading habit in them. However, when it comes to teaching kids English pronunciation, I believe all parents could benefit from some assistance. Mispronouncing words can not only lead to your child being misunderstood, but it can also cause them to feel embarrassed. If the situation persists, they could potentially develop a strong dislike for the English language. Hence, parents should understand how to teach pronunciation in order to assist children at home.

Good pronunciation means checking all three when you speak:

- Sounds: Sounds consist of consonants, diphthongs, and vowels.

- Stress: Stress is the emphasis on syllables.
- Intonation: Intonation is the rising and falling sounds when speaking.

Other than these, pace, pause, pitch, and volume also play a huge role in getting English pronunciation right.

Remember, there is no single method of teaching English pronunciation to all kids. Children in different age groups have different learning capacities. So, we must use the teaching methods accordingly.

Beginning Level English Learners:

Tongue Twisters - Tongue twisters are a great way to teach children the sounds of consonants, and at the same time, are a lot of fun, making sounds easier to remember. You can use tongue twisters like 'She sells seashells on the sea shore' and a few other great ones easily available online.

Songs - Songs are highly preferred way of teaching English pronunciation because they are an effortless learning tool. Children are naturally drawn towards songs. So, pick out children-friendly songs and listen to them with your child. Once they are familiar with the lyrics, encourage them to sing on their own.

Rhymes – Just like songs, children learn pronunciation quickly with rhymes. The musical element in poems for toddlers and preschoolers help them understand the timing of words, use proper intonation, and exercise stress where needed.

Vocabulary Training – When you teach your child new words, put emphasis on the correct pronunciation. Also, teach them the use of new words in context. However, make sure the words you teach are relevant. You can also use game-based learning methods to improve vocabulary in kids since vocabulary training can be a tiring experience for them.

Repetition – Repetition is a great method to reinforce learning. So, when you teach your child the pronunciation of a new word, ask them to repeat it every chance you get. It will help them commit the correct pronunciation to memory.

Minimal Pairs – Minimal pairs are addition and substitution exercises that help children understand how pronunciation works. For example, substituting the 'e' in 'pen' with an 'i' will make it 'pin'. This formula applies to other words as well, such as den, ten, etc. Consonant replacement also changes the pronunciation; for example, tin-thin and bin-pin. Teach your child these formulas to lay a strong foundation.

Intermediate Level English Learners:

Record and replay – encourage children to record and replay their sentences to review their own speech and identify the problem. Children between the ages of 9 and 15 are capable of self-correcting, which is also a great way to boost confidence.

Auditory discrimination – this activity involves differentiating between sounds, which is of great help to be able to pronounce words correctly. Give your child pair words and ask them to identify the sound. Good examples of pair words are mine-main or bay-boy-buy. To help them understand the words and pronunciations in context, encourage them to make sentences out of the words in the exercise; for example, 'the large doors are closed' and 'the lodge doors are closed.

Looking in the mirror – when kids look in the mirror while pronouncing new words, they can observe the lip and tongue movement, which helps in understanding the nature of sounds.

Advanced Level English Learners:

Chants – Chants are a great method of teaching English pronunciation with intonation. It helps in understanding the difference between the sounds of a question, statement, and exclamation. For example, take a group of sentences, such as:

- It is your class. (A falling tone).
- Is it your class? (A rising tone).
- It's your class? (A fall-rise tone that shows uncertainty).

Now use the correct intonation with each sentence and ask your child to repeat them with the right intonation as you demonstrated.

Connected Speech – Teenagers and pre-teens are smart enough to understand and learn connected speech words. For example, 'got to' is pronounced as 'gotta.' So, encourage them to listen to native speakers speak the English language and also use connected speech words with the right pronunciation.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Admit it - correct pronunciation in English is something that continues to benefit you. What I'm trying to say is that even if you are able to communicate effectively and have excelled in all of your English exams, if your pronunciation is not precise, your fluency may not be perceived as high by other English speakers. I understand why you did it. There are several challenging English vocabulary words. Your tongue may occasionally get twisted (and so does mine, even now).

Additionally, attempting to mimic the speaking style of native speakers is a major obstacle for non-native English speakers. English is a language where the pronunciation does not always match the spelling, making it difficult for learners. Today, you have the opportunity to end this!

Below are some proven methods and strategies that can greatly enhance your pronunciation in English and elevate your fluency to a higher standard.

❖ *Concentrating on the pronunciation of English*

Don't overanalyze the content of your words, instead, pay attention to your delivery. Think of this as a practice in shifting your attention. Are you merging sounds together, like saying "com-for-table" instead of "comf-ta-ble" or combining words improperly, like saying "aintchu" instead of "ain't you"? Are you accurately producing each sound? An effective method for evaluating your pronunciation is to stand in front of a mirror and pay attention to the movement of your mouth.

Additionally, you have the option to film yourself to accurately identify where your pronunciation mistakes are and understand what needs improvement. This method also allows you to perceive the impression you make on others when communicating, as it lets you observe other aspects of your "speech" like gestures and body posture.

❖ *Imitate others*

When recording yourself, you must compare your pronunciation to something in order to determine how close you are to achieving a truly native-like sound. I suggest selecting a preferred accent, such as British, and concentrating on correctly pronouncing each word as native speakers with that accent would do. Alternatively, you can simply choose a celebrity you admire or any fluent speaker and attempt to mimic their speech. Numerous resources are available to assist you in this endeavor, such as watching TV shows or YouTube videos, as well as listening to podcasts and interviews. Once again, pay attention to their speech and pronunciation of specific words that you may find difficult. No matter which path you take, mimicking those who speak English fluently can help enhance your pronunciation of the language, especially if you don't reside in an environment where English is the native language. It's about pushing yourself to actually speak like a native English speaker with minimal effort.

❖ *Read aloud*

As we read a book or online article, we unconsciously attempt to keep a consistent reading speed. Our reading experience is impacted if there are obstacles such as difficult words or lengthy sentences. Nonetheless, it is more subtle or hardly noticeable when we are not speaking out loud.

For a significant improvement in your English pronunciation quality, practice reading out loud. This method requires you to keep a consistent reading speed, pause as needed, and emphasize specific words just like a native speaker naturally does when talking. Above all, it requires you to pay attention to every sound you articulate, leading me to my next point...

❖ *Emphasize specific sounds even more*

I need to confess something minor (don't worry, it's a positive confession, I assure you). I believe the key to achieving a high level of accuracy similar to that of a native speaker is to avoid being lazy when speaking. This implies hitting every sound perfectly - what we discussed earlier.

As an English teacher, I am extremely strict about pronouncing specific English sounds, especially the two-way "th" sound.

The key point about "th" is that it can sound like either a "d" or a "t" based on the word. Nevertheless, it is not equivalent to just pronouncing the sounds "d" and "t" instead of the correct "th", as it alters the meaning of your statement entirely. Allow me to provide you with some instances.

"The correct pronunciation of "think" involves the sound "th", not "t" like in "tink".

The word "thought" is said with a "th" sound, not a "t" sound like in "taught".

The word "though" is pronounced with a sound of "th", not "d" like in "dough".

"Breathe" is said with a "th" sound, not a "d" sound like in "breed".

These individual sounds are what truly matter. A large number of my students initially find this simple trick to be very frustrating, but it yields benefits in the end! Students have come to me years after graduating to express gratitude for the challenging exercises I taught them, which they say greatly improved their communication skills.

❖ *Have a conversation with yourself*

Hmm... while the tips and strategies mentioned in this article are helpful, you may still be wondering where to find high-quality practice resources. The response is: no place at all!

Considering everything mentioned before, a great method for enhancing your English pronunciation is to have conversations with yourself, no matter how strange it may seem.

Therefore, discover a subject that captivates you and allows you to speak at great length, such as your preferred film or a significant worldwide problem. Additionally, determine the accent or speaker you wish to replicate. After that, position yourself in front of a mirror, film yourself, try to pay attention to each noise you make, and evaluate your performance. Following that, repeat and enhance. In the end, "repetition is the mother of learning"! This method is beneficial not only for enhancing your pronunciation but also for improving your overall communication abilities in English.

❖ *Engage in exercises with difficult phrases to pronounce*

Finally, we have tongue twisters, which are my preferred technique! Tongue twisters may appear difficult at first, but with practice, they become easier. Moreover, if you consistently work on them, you will naturally incorporate that level of accuracy into your daily conversations.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, when educating individuals on the English language vowels, we can focus on the length of the vowels.

Vowel Duration: Showing different lengths of vowels in a word by stretching rubber bands on longer vowels and letting them shrink on shorter ones. Next, allow the students to give it a shot.

An instance would be 'fifteen' having the rubber band stretched for the 'ee' vowel, while 'fifty' wouldn't stretch the band as both vowels are said quickly. Instructing students on syllables involves having them count syllables in a word by using their fingers or placing objects on a table to represent each syllable. Teachers can demonstrate syllable stress by clapping softly and loudly in accordance with each syllable of a word. An example of this would be the term 'beautiful' represented as loud-soft-soft. Start by practicing short lists of words with the same syllabic stress pattern, and then have your learners try listing other words with that pattern.

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